

IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE METHODS AND TOOLS IN LABORATORY EXERCISES IN THE DISCIPLINE OF ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING

Nikolay Vakrilov^{1*}, Nikoleta Shopova²

¹ Asst. Prof. PhD., Plovdiv University Paisii Hilendarski, BULGARIA, n_vakrilov@uni-plovdiv.bg

² M.S. student, Plovdiv University Paisii Hilendarski, BULGARIA, nikoletashopova088@gmail.com

*Corresponding author

Abstract

The development of students' professional skills is one of the main challenges in engineering education, as the technological world is rapidly changing and companies need innovation to improve their products and services. Today, engineering graduates must have sufficient practical experience and solid technical competencies in order to meet the high demands of the industry when entering the workforce. To overcome this issue, a strong feedback loop between academia and industry must be established. Only in this way engineering education can keep pace with new technological advancements and industry trends. Collaboration between academia and business can help develop new areas of research and facilitate the exchange of valuable practical experience to bridge the gaps in professional skills and competencies among future engineers. Another way to improve engineering education is through the implementation of new innovative technologies, which can enhance existing teaching methods. Technologies can provide online access to educational resources anytime and from anywhere in the world, and offer new ways to observe and analyze complex relationships and interactions in fundamental engineering disciplines that often challenge students during their studies. This article demonstrates how practical training in the subject "Electrical Engineering" can be improved through the use of innovative design tools, interactive simulations of electronic circuits, and multimedia learning resources to support preparation and enhance the understanding of complex engineering concepts during each lab session. To this end, new engineering-oriented laboratory exercises were developed. A project-based approach was used to structure the course content, allowing students to gain hands-on knowledge after each session by solving real-world engineering problems. It is expected that the proposed systematic approach to education will enable students to acquire in-depth knowledge in the field of "Electrical Engineering," skills for working with specialized engineering design and simulation software, teamwork abilities, and an independent understanding of professional responsibilities. In this way, students will maintain their motivation for learning and build up practical knowledge for their future careers in the labor market.

Keywords: E-learning, engineering student, electrical engineering.

1 INTRODUCTION

The global demand for engineers remains high, and there is a shortage of well-trained professionals across various industrial sectors. One of the main challenges in engineering education is the accumulation of sufficient practical experience and technical competencies to enable graduates to begin working immediately in today's complex industrial environment [Innovations in Engineering Education, 2016, pp. 4-11].

A fundamental problem in engineering education is the failure to take into account the professional requirements of industry.

For this reason, academic programs must be designed in a way that allows engineering students to develop the following competencies [Craig K., 2009, p. 9]:

- A basic understanding of engineering;
- In-depth expert knowledge;
- The ability to identify, formulate, and solve problems;
- The ability to apply a systematic approach to technical issues;
- Expertise in engineering design, engineering project management, and knowledge of the business environment;
- Skills for working with specialized information and technical documentation;
- Skills for working with specialized equipment and professional software for engineering design and simulations;
- Understanding of professional and ethical responsibilities;
- Ability to work independently and in teams;
- Workplace safety skills;
- Lifelong learning and a drive for career development.

These competencies can become a reality when universities provide students with an engaging environment that serves as an incubator for building engineering knowledge and skills [Rahman, MM. et al., 2022]. It is extremely important for students to solve practical problems with a focus on new technologies.

Providing students with a "hands-on" engineering experience in an educational setting is not an easy task, as it requires meeting real industrial standards related to specialized software and hardware in academic laboratories—something that is difficult even for universities with significant financial resources [Craig K., 2009].

Creating a learning environment where students can explore various scientific concepts and their application in engineering practice requires significant effort from both university technical faculties and industry. Since engineering problems are inherently multidisciplinary, solving them demands deep knowledge of multiple engineering disciplines, physics, and mathematics.

Striking a good balance between theory and practice is crucial for the training of well-prepared engineers [Ivanov, V. et al., 2024].

Solid preparation is essential to ensure that:

- Future engineers will quickly adapt to the modern complex work environment;
- They will be able to meet the needs of the high-tech industry and innovative companies.

To achieve this, it is necessary to implement innovative educational technologies and interactive teaching methods that provide new opportunities for observing complex physical processes and phenomena embedded in the fundamental disciplines studied in engineering programs.

This approach will help students more easily understand and absorb the learning material, keeping them motivated to study and continue building their expertise in the field of engineering [Electronic Design eMagazine, 2009].

This article presents opportunities for improving existing teaching methods in the discipline "Electrical Engineering," which is studied by all majors at the Faculty of Physics and Technology at Plovdiv University Paisii Hilendarski.

The application of such methods and technologies is highly beneficial, as it will enable students to more easily acquire the necessary knowledge and skills in the fields of electrical engineering and measurement technology - an essential foundation for successfully entering the engineering profession and achieving future career success.

2 METHODOLOGY

After analyzing the need for laboratory exercises aimed at improving students' professional skills in the field of electrical engineering, a new educational module titled "Bridge Methods for Measuring Resistance, Inductance, and Capacitance" was developed. This module includes the following laboratory exercises:

1. Measurement of resistance using a Wheatstone bridge;
2. Measurement of resistance using a Thomson bridge;
3. Bridge methods for measuring inductance and capacitance.

In the development of these laboratory exercises, the following considerations were taken into account:

- Modern methods and trends in the practical training of students;
- Addressing key problems from engineering practice during the execution of laboratory exercises;
- Use of modern technical tools for visualizing and clarifying the educational content of each laboratory exercise;
- Development of appropriate multimedia educational resources related to the content of each laboratory exercise;
- Selection of a suitable learning platform to facilitate the educational process and provide remote access to learning resources.

A project-based approach was used in structuring the educational content during the development of the laboratory exercises. The exercises include specially developed multimedia training materials with methodological guidelines covering SPICE simulations, as well as the implementation of a series of physical experiments using laboratory mock-ups for measuring resistance, inductance, and capacitance through different bridge circuits - their operation, adjustment, and application. Each circuit implementation discussed in the exercises is accompanied by a detailed methodology for its analytical calculation.

The educational content of the laboratory exercises and the developed multimedia resources have been uploaded to the DIPSEIL project-based learning platform (<https://v4.dipseil.net>). This ensures remote access to learning resources, allowing students to familiarize themselves with the materials before entering the laboratory. The DIPSEIL platform features a "Forum" module that enables asynchronous communication between students and instructors. The forum discussions are organized at the level of each laboratory exercise, which significantly facilitates communication on specific topics.

3 RESULTS

The newly developed educational module "Bridge Methods for Measuring Resistance, Inductance, and Capacitance" was piloted with students from an undergraduate engineering program during the first semester of their studies.

The students in the undergraduate program were divided into two groups. One group was trained using the existing educational resources, while the second group used the newly developed resources, which included methodological guidelines and multimedia educational materials created specifically for each laboratory exercise.

In the creation of the multimedia educational resources, emphasis was placed on student engagement with innovative software tools that have become standard in electrical engineering and electronics education.

Fig. 1 shows a screenshot from a multimedia resource demonstrating the use of the SPICE-based software Multisim, which was used to train students in simulating the behavior of electronic circuits during the laboratory exercises.

The video demonstrates all the steps for determining the unknown value of a resistor using one of the simplest bridge circuits - the Wheatstone bridge, through simulations in the Multisim software environment.

The interactive Multisim simulation used in the training allows students to observe how the resistance measured in a given electronic circuit can be correlated with another phenomenon that causes a change in resistance. This enables students to understand how various sensors work, such as: strain gauges, pressure sensors, relative humidity sensors, thermistors, and RTDs (Resistance Temperature Detectors) - all of which are widely used in engineering practice.

Fig. 1. Screenshot demonstrating the operation of a Wheatstone bridge in balanced mode within the SPICE-based Multisim software environment.

Fig. 2 shows a screenshot from a multimedia resource demonstrating the experimental procedure for measuring an unknown resistor, which students are required to physically implement on a laboratory prototype.

Fig. 2. Screenshot from the video tutorial showing the experiment for measuring an unknown resistor using a Wheatstone bridge.

The video tutorial provides step-by-step and detailed instructions for conducting the experiment to measure the unknown value of a resistor using the Wheatstone bridge circuit, which students are required to implement on a laboratory prototype. The video also demonstrates the necessary measuring instruments and their role in conducting the experiment.

After the pilot laboratory sessions with the different student groups, an assessment of the acquired knowledge was conducted.

The evaluation of student performance considered the following factors:

- Prepared laboratory reports - after each exercise, students submit a report with recorded data from the experiments and solutions to the assigned tasks;
- Submitted answers to control questions - these must be answered after completing the laboratory report and submitted to the instructor for evaluation;
- Final test - this includes a written test with theoretical questions, analytical calculations, and tasks related to the design and simulation of various bridge circuits.

When calculating the final grade, the final test carries the highest weight - 60%. The laboratory reports account for 20%, and the answers to the control questions make up the remaining 20% of the final grade.

A six-point grading scale is used to assess student performance, with the following grades: Excellent (6), Very Good (5), Good (4), Satisfactory (3), and Fail (2).

Fig. 3 and 4 show the final grades of the two student groups after the completion of the training.

Fig. 3. Final grades of students trained using the old educational resources.

Fig. 4. Final grades of students trained using the new educational resources, including methodological guidelines and multimedia instructional materials.

The students' results show that the approaches used in the development of the new educational resources

provide conditions for better assimilation of the learning material in the subject of Electrical Engineering. The grades of the second group of students, who were taught using the new educational resources, range from Very Good (4.5) to Excellent (5.75). The average grade achieved by this group is Very Good (5.11). In contrast, the first group, which was taught using the old educational resources, received lower grades, ranging from Good (3.75) to Very Good (5.25). The average grade of this group is Good (4.35).

In addition to the lower academic performance, the students from the first group did not demonstrate sufficient skills in working with measuring instruments and connecting the required bridge circuits. As a result, they needed assistance from the instructor when performing the assigned laboratory tasks. In comparison, the intervention of the instructor during the lab sessions of the second group was minimal. This proves that the newly developed educational resources offer a systematic and accessible way of acquiring new technical knowledge and skills.

4 CONCLUSIONS

To meet the educational needs in the course "Electrical Engineering" and to improve the training process for engineering students, the following laboratory exercises were developed:

1. Measurement of resistance using a Wheatstone bridge;
2. Measurement of resistance using a Thomson bridge;
3. Bridge methods for measuring inductance and capacitance.

In the development of the course content, the following aspects were taken into consideration:

- Existing challenges and current trends in the practical training of engineering students;
- Difficulties in understanding and assimilating the course material;
- Approaches to improving traditional methods for engineering education.

Based on an analysis of the needs for improving students' knowledge and skills, the following resources were developed:

1. Numerous examples that illustrate and clarify the course content;
2. Multimedia educational resources for each laboratory exercise, including:
 - Video tutorials with step-by-step, detailed instructions for working with the innovative Multisim software tools used to design and simulate processes in various bridge circuits for measuring resistance, inductance, and capacitance;
 - Video demonstrations of how to perform the tasks in the laboratory exercises;
 - Video guides for working with laboratory prototypes and the required measurement equipment.

The successful implementation of these new laboratory exercises is expected to:

- Increase students' interest in foundational engineering courses and help maintain their motivation throughout their studies;
- Ensure students gain hands-on experience with measurement equipment and modern specialized software for circuit design and analysis-essential components of engineering practice;
- Provide the necessary engineering competencies and practical skills required for their future careers in industry.

REFERENCE LIST

Innovations in Engineering Education - Inspiring & Preparing Our Engineers for the 21st Century, (2016). Lloyd's Register Foundation. pp. 4-11. https://www.ucl.ac.uk/centre-for-engineering-education/sites/centre-for-engineering-education/files/ucl_cee_lrf_report_0.pdf

Craig, K. (2009). Transformational Engineering Education. College of Engineering. Marquette University

- Rahman, M. M., Ferdousi, U. S., Hasan, T., Sharmin, T. (2022). Challenges in Engineering Education: A Review. Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Industrial & Mechanical Engineering and Operations. 1061-1063. Dhaka. Bangladesh
- Ivanov, V., Pavlenko, I., Evtuhov, A., Trojanowska, J. (2024). Major Challenges in Engineering Education. In: Augmented Reality for Engineering Graphics. Springer Tracts in Mechanical Engineering. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-44641-2_1
- Electronic Design eMagazine. "What's wrong with engineering education?". (2009). <https://www.electronicdesign.com/technologies/communications/article/21767906/whats-wrong-with-engineering-education>